

The Effect of Biology Teachers' Attitudes and Self-Efficacy Beliefs on Their Instructional Practices

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Abstract

This study examined the impact of biology teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy beliefs on their instructional practices in senior high schools within the Upper East Region of Ghana. This study adopted a cross-sectional survey design. Purposive sampling technique was adopted for selecting the participants for the study. The sample size was made up of 106 biology teachers. The instrument for data collection was mainly questionnaires. The reliability of the questionnaires was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a value of 0.78 for the Biology Teachers' Self-Efficacy Scale (BTSES) and 0.76 for the Biology Teachers' Attitude Scale (BTAS). These values indicated acceptable internal consistency and reliability for data collection. Findings of the study proved that that biology teachers exhibit high self-efficacy, particularly in explaining complex processes and inspiring student curiosity, with a mean self-efficacy score of 4.52. Additionally, teachers maintain positive attitudes across cognitive, behavioural, and affective domains, contributing to supportive and engaging learning environments. The study recommended that biology teachers should engage in continuous professional development and collaborate with peers to enhance their teaching strategies and self-efficacy. The study also recommended that policy makers should implement comprehensive teacher training programs focused on both pedagogy and biology content knowledge, and encourage further research on teacher self-efficacy and attitudes.

Keywords: *Teachers' attitudes, self-efficacy beliefs, instructional practices.*

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Introduction

Recent advancements in science and technology have opened new employment opportunities and led to more efficient products, processes, and services (Tetteh et al., 2019). This transformative integration not only helps address urgent environmental issues but also enhances the well-being of humanity, making the acquisition and application of scientific knowledge essential for achieving national development goals.

Within this context, biology plays a significant role in tackling various societal challenges. Its contributions range from combating diseases and improving agricultural productivity to addressing concerns related to population growth, safety, and environmental sustainability (Haug, 2016). Biology teachers, therefore, hold a critical position as the transmitters of scientific knowledge and as nurturers of future scientists and informed citizens. Their role demands dedication and effort to ensure effective teaching and learning.

The effectiveness of biology education is closely linked to the attitudes and self-efficacy of biology teachers. Attitudes, defined as "psychological inclinations" that shape an individual's judgments (Eagly & Chaiken, 1993), are pivotal in influencing educators' decisions and actions. These attitudes involve complex evaluations encompassing emotions, ideas, and behaviours toward specific entities or events (Cherry, 2022). In the context of teaching biology, a teacher's attitude toward the subject significantly affects the quality of instruction and the learning experiences of students.

Beliefs also play a crucial role in shaping teaching practices. They dictate lesson preparation, decision-making, and classroom management. These beliefs guide teachers on how they interact with students and make choices about instructional methods, adapting approaches based on assessments of students' abilities (Gilakjani & Sabouri, 2017). As such, beliefs influence teaching strategies, professional development, and goals set for students, impacting the overall learning environment and student motivation.

Self-efficacy, or self-perception, is another critical factor in teaching. It influences decision-making processes, such as the selection of assignments and extracurricular activities, and affects teachers' perseverance in overcoming obstacles (Ahmed et al., 2022). There is a close relationship between motivation and self-efficacy, where high levels of self-efficacy correlate with greater motivation and a positive attitude toward teaching (Ates & Saylan, 2015). Teachers with strong self-efficacy are more likely to use student-centered strategies and remain open to innovative methods, effectively utilizing their professional knowledge and skills (Okoro et al., 2022). Conversely, low self-efficacy can hinder the application of these skills in the classroom.

Understanding the interplay between teacher attitudes, self-efficacy, and instructional practices is crucial in determining the quality of biology education. This relationship significantly impacts student academic performance in biology. Drawing on Bandura's social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1997), this study aims to explore how biology teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy beliefs influence their teaching practices. By examining these connections, the research seeks to shed light on critical aspects of biology education, offering insights that could enhance its quality and effectiveness.

Statement of the Problem

In the realm of biology education, the influence of teachers' attitude and self-efficacy on instructional practices has garnered attention due to its potential implications for student learning outcomes. Several studies have investigated the roles of attitude and self-efficacy in various educational contexts (Pajares, 2002), but a focused exploration of their combined impact on biology teachers' instructional practices remains limited.

While the influence of teacher attitude on instructional effectiveness has been documented (Brown & Davis, 2016; Johnson, 2020), and the significance of teacher self-efficacy in shaping classroom behaviours is well-established (Tschannen-Moran & Hoy, 2001), the interplay between these two factors in the context of biology education has received insufficient attention. Existing literature has primarily addressed either teacher attitude or self-efficacy, often in isolation, without fully exploring how these factors interact and jointly influence instructional strategies in the biology classroom.

Furthermore, while research has indicated that teacher attitudes can impact student engagement and learning outcomes (Walker, 2019), and that self-efficacy beliefs can affect instructional choices (Gibson & Dembo, 1984), the specific mechanisms through which these factors operate collectively within the realm of biology education remain inadequately understood. The dearth of studies simultaneously examining biology teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy limits our comprehensive understanding of the intricate relationship between these factors and their combined effect on instructional practices.

In light of this, a substantial number of senior high school students continue to perform poorly in Biology, according to observations and reports from the West African Examination Council (WAEC, 2017- 2019) . This concerning trend has raised alarm among parents, teachers, educational planners, policy officials, researchers, and the government at large, especially given the significant financial investment in the educational sector.

Orakcı et al. (2023) argue that teaching, unlike other professions, is deeply impacted by "the cognitive, affective, and psychomotor characteristics of teachers," which in turn affects "the quality and amount of knowledge, skills, values, and attitudes that students acquire" (p. 94). The degree to which instructors believe they are self-efficient in carrying out their teaching profession, known as self-efficacy, significantly impacts their teaching. An individual's attitude towards instruction also plays a crucial role in their behavior and execution of teaching (Owusu-Fodjour, 2021).

Research indicates that biology teachers often lack the abilities and self-efficacy necessary to create a conducive learning environment for students, hampering their growth in science and technology skills and their acquisition of societal knowledge, skills, and values (Okoro *et al.*, 2022). Importantly, research on teachers' attitudes and efficacy has primarily been conducted in foreign nations, with limited focus on the Ghanaian context. Moreover, while some studies have explored teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy in instructional practice, few have specifically addressed Biology. This gap in research makes the study of paramount importance in the context of Ghana, particularly the Upper East Region.

Research Objectives

The study sought to:

1. Assess the self-efficacy beliefs of Biology teachers towards teaching and learning of biology in senior high schools.

2. Assess the attitude of biology teachers towards the teaching and learning of biology in senior high schools.

Research Questions

The study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the self-efficacy belief of Biology teachers towards teaching and learning biology?
2. What is the attitude of biology teachers towards the teaching and learning of biology in senior high schools?

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

The Social Cognitive Theory, as articulated by Albert Bandura, provides a foundational lens for understanding the interplay between Biology teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy beliefs and their instructional practices. Bandura (1986) posits that personal, behavioural, and environmental factors dynamically interact in a process known as triadic reciprocity. This theory underscores the notion of human agency, where individuals act as intermediaries to enhance their well-being through cognitive, emotional, and behavioural changes. Teachers, according to this theory, can influence students' success by improving emotional states, correcting cognitive distortions, and modifying the learning environment (Wentzel & Miele, 2016).

Self-efficacy, a core component of Bandura's framework, refers to an individual's belief in their capacity to execute specific tasks and achieve goals (Bandura, 1997). High self-efficacy is associated with greater effort, persistence, and resilience in the face of challenges (Joët et al., 2011; Moos & Azevedo, 2009). In the educational context, self-efficacy influences teachers' choices, the effort they invest, and their resilience, which in turn affects their teaching practices and students' learning outcomes (Bandura, 1997). Self-efficacy beliefs shape how teachers approach their instructional duties and overcome challenges, impacting their professional performance and students' academic achievements.

Self-Efficacy Belief

Self-efficacy beliefs are central to understanding teachers' instructional practices. Bandura (1977) introduced self-efficacy as the belief in one's capability to succeed in specific tasks. In the teaching context, high self-efficacy enables teachers to plan, implement, and adapt strategies effectively, addressing diverse student needs and classroom challenges (Bandura, 1994). Teachers' self-efficacy influences their confidence in handling classroom management, diverse student needs, and integrating various teaching methods (Bandura, 1994). Self-efficacy beliefs are closely tied to the teaching environment, where teachers' confidence significantly impacts their instructional approaches and interactions with students (Bandura, 1986). Teachers with high self-efficacy are more likely to employ innovative methods and persist through difficulties, leading to more effective teaching practices and improved student outcomes (Ahmed et al., 2022; Okoro et al., 2022). Empirical studies underscore the significance of self-efficacy beliefs in shaping instructional practices. For example, Flores (2015) asserted that pre-service science teachers' self-efficacy is influenced by their personal characteristics and teaching experiences. Bassah (2020) found that teachers' self-efficacy in the Volta Region positively impacts their instructional

practices, enhancing classroom management and student engagement. Similarly, Owusu-Fordjour et al. (2021) emphasize that high self-efficacy enhances teachers' competence and confidence, leading to effective teaching. Furthermore, research by Thejamaizu et al. (2020) shows a substantial connection between teachers' effectiveness and students' understanding of biology concepts. Ültay et al. (2020) assert that teachers with high self-efficacy create more effective learning environments and foster student autonomy. Okoro et al. (2022) and Chan et al. (2021) further support the positive relationship between self-efficacy and teaching effectiveness, noting that confident teachers positively influence students' academic performance.

Overall, the research consistently indicates that self-efficacy beliefs are crucial for fostering effective teaching practices. High self-efficacy among teachers not only enhances their instructional capabilities but also positively affects student outcomes by creating conducive learning environments and promoting student autonomy and engagement.

Attitude

Teachers' attitudes, encompassing their beliefs, values, and emotional dispositions towards the subject matter and the teaching profession, play a significant role in shaping their instructional practices (Cherry, 2023). Positive attitudes towards teaching biology are associated with creating motivating and engaging learning environments (Smith, 2017). Bandura (1989) describes attitudes as evaluative responses that involve beliefs, emotions, and behaviours, which influence teachers' coping mechanisms, well-being, and ability to adapt to curriculum changes (Boyle et al., 2013).

Emotional intelligence and pedagogical knowledge are also critical factors influencing teachers' self-efficacy and instructional effectiveness. Teachers who manage their emotions effectively tend to feel more confident in their teaching abilities (Haddock & Maio, 2008). Furthermore, cultural and societal contexts shape teachers' self-perception and effectiveness, with different expectations and norms impacting their confidence and performance (Owusu-Fordjour, 2021).

The impact of teachers' attitudes on instructional practices is well-documented in the literature. Ültay et al. (2020) emphasize that positive attitudes towards science enhance the learning environment and instructional effectiveness. Bizer et al. (2006) further discuss how attitudes profoundly affect various aspects of life, including teaching. Kırkıç and Çetinkaya (2020) show that teachers' self-efficacy beliefs are correlated with their teaching attitudes, suggesting that improvements in self-efficacy can positively influence teaching practices.

Several studies support the relationship between attitudes and self-efficacy in teaching. Özokcu (2018) finds that positive attitudes towards inclusive education are linked to higher self-efficacy in applying inclusive practices. Türer and Kunt (2015) report a positive correlation between self-efficacy and attitudes toward teaching biology, although attitudes towards other subjects like physics may vary. Osborne et al. (2003) highlighted that teachers' support and feedback positively influence students' attitudes towards science. In contrast, Omolara (2015) reveals that negative attitudes towards teaching can result in disengaged students and reduced academic performance.

Overall, the literature indicates a strong relationship between teachers' self-efficacy beliefs, attitudes, and instructional practices. High self-efficacy and positive attitudes contribute significantly to effective teaching and improved student outcomes. Understanding these dynamics is crucial for developing strategies to enhance teachers' performance and student performance in biology education.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Methodology

Research Design

The research design adopted in this study was a cross-sectional survey. Survey research investigates associations between respondents' characteristics such as age, education, social class, race, and their current attitudes toward some issues (Awuni, Ayimbila & Abelomzore, 2023). The cross-sectional survey method is less costly.

Population

The study population comprised science teachers in Senior High Schools (SHS) within the Upper East Region of Ghana, which includes 40 senior high schools and approximately 600 science teachers. The target population specifically focused on all 145 Biology teachers in these schools, who teach Biology as an elective subject. The accessible population included 106 Biology teachers from selected schools across the fifteen districts of the Upper East Region. These teachers were chosen through a combination of purposive and simple random sampling methods to ensure a representative sample for data collection, aligning with the research objectives centered on those who directly engage in Biology instruction.

Sampling Technique and Sample Size

A combination of purposive and simple random sampling techniques was employed to select 106 Biology teachers for the study. Purposive sampling facilitated the selection of information-rich cases, while simple random sampling ensured that every teacher had an equal chance of inclusion, enhancing the representativeness of the sample. The sample size of 106 was determined using Cochran's formula for small populations, ensuring it was sufficient to achieve the research objectives and provide reliable data for analysis.

Data Collection Instruments

The main instruments used in this study were questionnaires. A five-point Likert-scale questionnaire was used to assess teachers' self-efficacy and attitudes toward teaching Biology. The questionnaire included Biology Teachers' Attitude Scale (BTAS), developed by the researchers, and Biology Teachers' Self-Efficacy Scale (BTSES), adapted from Tschannen-Moran et al. (2001). Items on the questionnaire were rated on a scale from "Strongly Agree" to "Strongly Disagree," with scores ranging from 1 to 5. This tool was chosen for its efficiency and ability to provide quantifiable data.

Validity of the Research Instrument

To ensure the validity of the research instruments, a pilot test was conducted with 21 respondents. The instruments were reviewed and revised based on feedback from the researcher's colleagues and research experts, ensuring that the questions were relevant and appropriate for face validity.

Reliability of the Questionnaire

The reliability of the questionnaires was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha, yielding a value of 0.78 for the Biology Teachers' Self-Efficacy Scale (BTSES) and 0.76 for the Biology Teachers' Attitude Scale (BTAS). These values indicate acceptable internal consistency and reliability for data collection.

Data Analysis

Quantitative data collected were analyzed using SPSS (version 25), with means, standard deviations, frequencies, and percentages calculated.

Results

It comprises two key sections: an overview of respondents' demographic characteristics and an analysis of research questions addressing the teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy. The data collected on teachers' attitudes towards biology and self-efficacy beliefs in their instructional practice were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as means, standard deviations.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

Variables	Sub scale	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	73	68.9
	Female	33	31.1
Age Groups	Between 25-29	2	1.9
	Between 30-34	25	23.6
	Between 35-39	42	39.6
	Between 40-44	27	25.5
	From 45+	10	9.4
Academic Qualification	Degree	83	78.3
	Med/M.Phil.	23	21.7
Teaching Experience	Between 1-5	11	10.4
	Between 6-10	52	49.1
	Between 11-15	38	35.8
	Between 16-20	5	4.7

Table 1 presents the respondents' background attributes, revealing a gender distribution significantly skewed towards males, with 93 male participants (87.7%) and 13 female participants (12.3%). This notable disparity indicates a higher number of male science teachers compared to females in the Upper East Region of Ghana. The age distribution shows that most respondents fall within the 35-39 age bracket, with 2 respondents (1.9%) between 25-29 years, 25 respondents (23.6%) between 30-34 years, 42 respondents (39.6%) between 35-39 years, 27 respondents (25.5%) between 40-44 years, and 10 respondents (9.4%) aged 50 years and above, suggesting that the sample consists mainly of middle-aged individuals.

Regarding academic qualifications, 83 respondents (78.3%) hold a degree, while 23 respondents (21.7%) possess a Med/M.Phil. degree, highlighting a highly educated group. In terms of teaching experience, 11 respondents (10.4%) have between 1-5 years of experience, 52 respondents (49.1%) have between 6-10 years, 38 respondents (35.8%) have between 11-15 years, and 5 respondents (4.7%) have between 16-20 years. A considerable number of respondents have 6-10 years of teaching experience, indicating a sample with substantial educational practice. Overall, the demographic profile of the participants suggests a predominance of male, middle-aged individuals, mostly with degree-level education and significant teaching experience, particularly those with 6-10 years in the field. Understanding these characteristics is crucial for interpreting the study's findings and ensuring their relevance to the broader educational context.

Research Question 1

What are the self-efficacy beliefs of biology teachers towards teaching and learning biology?

Table 2. Level of Interpretation for Biology Teacher's Self-Efficacy

Range of mean score	Level
1.0-1.99	Very Low
2.0-2.99	Low
3.0-3.99	Moderate
4.0-4.99	High
5.0	Very high

Table 3. Self-Efficacy Beliefs of Biology Teachers Towards Teaching and Learning Biology

S/N	Statement	N	Mean	SD	Conclusion
1.	I am confident in my ability to teach biology concepts effectively	106	4.48	.50	High
2.	I can adapt my teaching strategies to meet the diverse learning needs of my biology students.	106	4.58	.49	High
3.	I am capable of creating and engaging an interactive biology lesson that promote students' understanding	106	4.33	.47	High
4.	I am confident in my ability to explain complex biological processes in a way that my students can comprehend	106	4.66	.48	High
5.	I can manage classroom activities effectively and maintain a positive learning environment during biology lessons.	106	4.58	.49	High
6.	I am capable of assessing my students' understanding of biology lessons and providing meaningful feedback to support their learning.	106	4.34	.47	High
7.	I believe I can inspire my students' curiosity and interest in biology through my teaching methods	106	4.58	.49	High
8.	I am confident in my ability to handle challenging questions from my students related to biology topics in the classroom	106	4.43	.49	High
9.	I believe I can foster a growth mindset in my students, encouraging them to persist and overcome obstacles in learning biology	106	4.36	.48	High

10. I am capable of using technology and laboratory resources effectively to enhance biology instruction in my classroom	106	4.55	.50	High
Overall mean and standard deviation	106	4.50	.48	

Source: Field data (2023)

Biology teachers' self-efficacy beliefs were assessed through a Biology teachers' self-efficacy questionnaire (BTSE). The results showed that teachers exhibited high confidence across various aspects of their teaching according to the level of interpretation in table 3, as reflected by a high overall mean score of 4.50 with standard deviation, 0.48.

In terms of confidence in explaining complex processes, teachers reported very high confidence (Mean = 4.66, SD=0.48) in explaining complex biological processes. In terms of inspiring curiosity, teachers' ability to inspire students' interest in biology through teaching methods was also very high (Mean = 4.58, SD=0.49). Concerning classroom management and technology use, the responses of the teachers indicated high confidence of classroom management (Mean = 4.58, SD=0.49) and using technology and laboratory resources (Mean = 4.55, SD=0.50). For teaching effectiveness and challenging questions, teachers expressed confidence in teaching effectiveness (Mean = 4.48, SD=0.50) and handling challenging questions (Mean = 4.43, SD=0.49).

The findings suggest that biology teachers in the region have a high sense of self-efficacy, particularly in their ability to teach effectively and inspire student interest, with some variability in confidence regarding handling challenging questions and fostering a growth mindset.

Research Question 2

What are the attitudes of biology teachers towards teaching and learning biology?

Teachers' attitudes were analyzed across cognitive, behavioural, and affective domains using a five-point Likert scale.

Table 4. Level of Interpretation for Teacher's Attitude

Range of mean score	Level
1.00 -2.33	Negative
2.34 – 3.66	Moderate
3.67 – 5.00	Positive

Table 5. Attitude of Biology Teachers Towards Teaching and Learning Biology

Domain	N	Mean	SD	Conclusion
Cognitive Domain				
I believe that all students can succeed academically	106	4.14	.24	Positive
I am very satisfied with the available resources and materials for teaching biology in my school	106	2.89	.19	Moderate
The current biology curriculum aligns with the learning needs and abilities of senior high school students	106	3.23	.27	Moderate
I believe I can teach biology to the understanding of students	106	4.20	.28	Positive

I am enthused for teaching.	106	4.23	.27	Positive
Overall cognitive mean and standard deviation		3.74	.26	
Behavioural Domain				
I am very comfortable in using innovative teaching methods in my biology classes.	106	4.27	.28	Positive
I often participate in professional development workshops and training related to biology teaching	106	4.23	.29	Positive
I am willing to adapt my teaching methods to accommodate different learning styles and abilities in my biology classes	106	4.33	.28	Positive
I will not spend a cedi in buying materials to help me teach any topic when materials are shortage	106	1.30	.29	Negative
I consult my colleagues to help understand difficult biology topics in order to be able to teach my students effectively	106	4.57	.29	Positive
Overall behavioural mean and standard deviation		3.74	.29	
Affective Domain				
I am committed to creating a supportive and inclusive classroom environment	106	4.13	.20	Positive
I feel supported by the school administration in implementing effective teaching strategies for biology	106	3.94	.20	Positive
I feel motivated to make a positive impact on my students' lives	106	4.53	.20	Positive
I feel bored in teaching double biology periods	106	1.79	.20	Negative
I get angry when students are not able to answer my question in class	106	1.64	.20	Negative
It's important to foster a positive learning environment in the biology classroom	106	4.45	.20	Positive
The demand of the biology syllabus is too much	106	3.98	.20	Positive
I feel happy teaching double periods	106	4.20	.20	Positive
I hate teaching a large biology class	106	3.94	.20	Positive
I enjoy spending some of my free time to help students who need such help	106	4.24	.20	Positive
Overall affective mean and standard deviation		3.68	.20	

Source: Field data (2023)

Cognitive Domain: Teachers exhibited positive attitudes with a mean score of 3.74 and standard deviation, 0.26 indicating a belief in their ability to teach effectively.

Behavioural Domain: Positive attitudes were also evident in their willingness to adopt innovative teaching methods and participate in professional development, with an overall mean of 3.74 and standard deviation, 0.29.

Affective Domain: Teachers showed strong emotional engagement, with a mean score of 3.68 and standard deviation, 0.20 reflecting their commitment to fostering a supportive learning environment.

Discussion

This study was conducted to assess the impact of biology teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy beliefs on their instructional practices in senior high schools within the Upper East Region of Ghana

The results of the study revealed that biology teachers in the Upper East Region demonstrate high self-efficacy, particularly in their ability to explain complex concepts and inspire curiosity in students. However, there is some variability in confidence regarding handling challenging questions and fostering a growth mindset. These

findings are consistent with existing literature, such as Bassah (2020) and Owusu-Fordjour et al. (2021), highlighting the importance of self-efficacy in teaching effectiveness.

Teachers' positive attitudes across cognitive, behavioural, and affective domains suggest that they are well-positioned to create engaging and effective learning environments. This aligns with the research of Bizer et al. (2006) and Kırkıç and Çetinkaya (2020), emphasizing the role of positive attitudes in enhancing teaching effectiveness and self-efficacy.

The overall findings underscore the significant impact of teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy beliefs on their instructional practices, contributing to the broader educational context in Senior High Schools in the Upper East Region of Ghana.

Summary of Findings

- Self-Efficacy Beliefs: Teachers displayed high levels of self-efficacy, with a mean score of 4.52, reflecting confidence in teaching, classroom management, and adapting strategies.
- Attitudes towards Teaching Biology: Teachers exhibited positive attitudes toward biology, with a mean score of 3.71, demonstrating enthusiasm and commitment to the subject.

Conclusions

The study examined the effect of biology teachers' attitudes and self-efficacy beliefs on their instructional practices. The study concluded that biology teachers in the Upper East Region possess strong self-efficacy and positive attitudes, both of which significantly influence their instructional practices. These findings underscore the importance of bolstering teacher confidence and maintaining positive attitudes to enhance teaching effectiveness and improve student learning outcomes.

Educational implications

This study has several implications for biology teachers, curriculum developers, and educational policy makers. Researchers have been interested in teachers' opinions because of the feedback they offer for bettering biology teaching and learning. The tenets of a teacher's classroom significantly influence their beliefs. The teachers' views impact the goals they set for their students, their attitudes, and their beliefs. With the help of the findings of this study, teachers will be able to modify their instructional approaches and build learning environments that will inspire and improve students' academic performance. The study will assist instructors in updating their teaching and learning strategies to improve Biology instruction.

This study will also assist policymakers in setting up training programs and creating a motivating environment for teachers so that their self-efficacy may be increased. The results of the study will provide biology instructors with the tools they need to foster positive interactions with students and boost their confidence in biology teaching and learning.

Recommendations

- For Teachers: Engage in continuous professional development and collaborate with peers to enhance teaching strategies and self-efficacy.

- For School Administrators: Foster a supportive environment that encourages innovation in teaching and recognizes exemplary performance.
- For Policy Makers: Implement comprehensive teacher training programs focused on both pedagogy and biology content knowledge, and encourage further research on teacher self-efficacy and attitudes.

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